

A Study on the Correlation between Breast Cancer Grading and Staging with Hormone Receptor Status in Rural India

Aman¹, Kumar Ratnesh², Chandra Mohan Sinha³

¹PG Student, Department of General Surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

²Professor, Department of General Surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

³Professor, Department of General Surgery, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College and Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Athira Sanal Kumar

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Abstract:

Background: Breast cancer is the most common malignancy among women globally, with increasing incidence in rural India. Understanding the correlation between tumor characteristics and hormone receptor status is crucial for effective management and improved patient outcomes.

Aim: This study aimed to investigate the correlation between breast cancer grading and staging with hormone receptor status in a rural Indian population.

Methods: A study with a retrospective observational design was carried out on eighty female patients with breast cancer. SPSS version 23.0 was used to gather and analyse information on the histopathological grades, clinical stages, and hormone receptor statuses (ER, PR, and HER2). The correlation between the variables was assessed using Chi-square testing and Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Results: The average age of the study population was 52.3 years, and 65% of them were postmenopausal. Clinically, 50% of tumours were Stage II, while histopathologically, 55% were Grade II. HER2 positivity was detected in 25% of cases, but ER and PR positivity were seen in 60% and 50% of cases, respectively. Higher histopathological grades and ER status showed a significant inverse connection ($r = -0.38$, $p < 0.01$). Negative ER and PR statuses were substantially correlated with advanced clinical stages. More often, higher-grade and advanced-stage tumours were HER2 positive.

Conclusion: The study demonstrated significant correlations between higher histopathological grades and advanced clinical stages with negative hormone receptor status and positive HER2 status. These findings highlight the aggressive nature of hormone receptor-negative and HER2-positive breast cancers in the rural Indian population.

Recommendations: Efforts should be made to enhance early detection and provide access to targeted therapies in rural areas. Tailored screening programs and education on breast cancer awareness are crucial to improve outcomes.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Histopathological Grade, Clinical Stage, Hormone Receptor Status.

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Introduction

As the most prevalent disease in women globally, breast cancer poses a serious threat to public health. Breast cancer is still the most common cause of cancer-related death among women, even with advancements in early identification and treatment. This is especially true in underdeveloped nations where access to healthcare is frequently restricted. The incidence of breast cancer has been increasing in India, with rural areas being disproportionately affected by the disease because of delayed detection and restricted access to specialised care [1].

It is essential to comprehend the biology behaviour of breast cancer in order to create successful treatment plans. Clinical staging and histopathological grading are well-established prognostic variables that influence treatment choices and forecast patient outcomes. Tumour differentiation is graded according to histopathological grading, which assigns a grade: Grade I (well-differentiated), Grade II (moderately differentiated), and Grade III (poorly differentiated). Clinical staging is determined by the TNM classification system, taking into account tumour size, involvement of lymph nodes, and distant metastases. Important details regarding the

severity and dissemination of the illness are provided by both grading and staging [2].

Breast cancer is further classified into subtypes with different biological behaviours and responses to treatment based on the status of hormone receptors, such as the human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2), progesterone receptor (PR), and oestrogen receptor (ER). The majority of cases of breast cancer are ER and PR-positive tumours, which are typically linked to a better prognosis and responsiveness to hormone therapy. On the other hand, breast tumours that are HER2-positive and triple-negative (meaning they do not express HER2, PR, or ER) tend to be more aggressive and have fewer alternatives for targeted treatment [3].

Previous studies have demonstrated significant correlations between hormone receptor status and tumor characteristics. For instance, higher histopathological grades and advanced clinical stages are frequently observed in ER-negative and HER2-positive tumors, indicating a more aggressive disease course [4]. However, most of these studies have been conducted in urban settings or high-income countries, with limited data available from rural populations, where breast cancer management poses unique challenges.

This study aims to investigate the correlation between breast cancer grading and staging with hormone receptor status.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in a rural medical center in India, which provides comprehensive cancer care services to the local population. The study spanned from January 2022 to December 2023 were included in the study.

Participants: A total of 80 female patients diagnosed with breast cancer.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients with histopathologically confirmed breast cancer.

- Availability of complete medical records including hormone receptor status (ER, PR, and HER2).

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with recurrent or metastatic breast cancer at initial presentation.
- Incomplete medical records or missing hormone receptor status.
- Patients who received neoadjuvant chemotherapy prior to biopsy.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was employed. Potential information bias was reduced by ensuring that all data were collected and verified by trained medical personnel using standardized protocols.

Data Collection: Data were collected from patient medical records and the hospital's cancer registry. Information on demographic details, histopathological grade, clinical stage, and hormone receptor status were extracted and recorded in a pre-designed data collection sheet.

Procedure: The Nottingham grading method was used to establish the histological grade of breast cancer. Clinical staging was carried out in compliance with the staging manual of the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC). Immunohistochemistry (IHC) staining for the oestrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR), and HER2 status was used to determine the hormone receptor status.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The tumour features and patient demographics were determined using descriptive statistics. Using Pearson's correlation coefficient and Chi-square tests, the relationship between hormone receptor status and breast cancer staging and grading was assessed. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance.

Result

The study included 80 female patients with a mean age of 52.3 years (range: 28-75 years). The majority of patients were postmenopausal (65%), while 35% were premenopausal. The histopathological grades and clinical stages of breast cancer among the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Histopathological Grades and Clinical Stages

Characteristic	Number of Patients (n=80)	Percentage (%)
Histopathological Grade		
Grade I	16	20%
Grade II	44	55%
Grade III	20	25%
Clinical Stage		
Stage I	12	15%

Stage II	40	50%
Stage III	20	25%
Stage IV	8	10%

The hormone receptor status of the breast cancer cases is detailed in Table 2. ER-positive and PR-positive cases were predominant, with 60% and 50% respectively, while 25% of the cases were HER2-positive.

Table 2: Hormone Receptor Status

Hormone Receptor Status	Number of Patients (n=80)	Percentage (%)
ER-positive	48	60%
ER-negative	32	40%
PR-positive	40	50%
PR-negative	40	50%
HER2-positive	20	25%
HER2-negative	60	75%

A significant inverse correlation was observed between histopathological grade and ER status ($r = -0.38$, $p < 0.01$). Grade III tumors were more likely to be ER-negative (70%) compared to Grade I tumors (10%). Similar trends were noted with PR status, with Grade III tumors being predominantly PR-negative (65%).

Table 3: Histopathological Grade and Hormone Receptor Status

Histopathological Grade	ER-positive (%)	ER-negative (%)	PR-positive (%)	PR-negative (%)
Grade I	85% (n=14)	15% (n=2)	75% (n=12)	25% (n=4)
Grade II	55% (n=24)	45% (n=20)	50% (n=22)	50% (n=22)
Grade III	30% (n=6)	70% (n=14)	35% (n=7)	65% (n=13)

An analysis of clinical stage and hormone receptor status revealed a significant correlation between advanced stage and negative hormone receptor status (ER and PR). Stage III and IV tumors were predominantly ER-negative (65%) and PR-negative (60%).

Table 4: Clinical Stage and Hormone Receptor Status

Clinical Stage	ER-positive (%)	ER-negative (%)	PR-positive (%)	PR-negative (%)
Stage I	75% (n=9)	25% (n=3)	70% (n=8)	30% (n=4)
Stage II	65% (n=26)	35% (n=14)	60% (n=24)	40% (n=16)
Stage III	35% (n=7)	65% (n=13)	40% (n=8)	60% (n=12)
Stage IV	25% (n=2)	75% (n=6)	25% (n=2)	75% (n=6)

HER2-positive status was found to be associated with higher histopathological grades and advanced clinical stages. Approximately 40% of Grade III tumors were HER2-positive compared to only 10% of Grade I tumors. Similarly, Stage III and IV tumors showed higher HER2 positivity (35%).

Table 5: HER2 Status and Tumor Characteristics

Tumor Characteristic	HER2-positive (%)	HER2-negative (%)
Grade I	10% (n=2)	90% (n=14)
Grade II	25% (n=11)	75% (n=33)
Grade III	40% (n=8)	60% (n=12)
Stage I	8% (n=1)	92% (n=11)
Stage II	25% (n=10)	75% (n=30)
Stage III	35% (n=7)	65% (n=13)
Stage IV	25% (n=2)	75% (n=6)

The statistical analysis using SPSS version 23.0 revealed significant correlations between higher histopathological grades and advanced clinical stages with negative hormone receptor status (ER and PR) and positive HER2 status. Pearson's correlation coefficient and Chi-square tests confirmed these associations with p-values < 0.05 , indicating statistical significance.

Discussion

In a rural Indian population, the purpose of this study was to look at the relationship between hormone receptor status and breast cancer stage and grading. Eighty female breast cancer patients

were included in the analysis, which produced important results that advance our knowledge of the features of breast cancer in this population.

The mean age of the study population was 52.3 years, and postmenopausal women made up a bigger percentage of the population (65%). According to histopathology, Grade II tumours accounted for the majority of cases (55%), followed by Grade III (25%) and Grade I (20%). Clinically, 50% of the tumours were in Stage II, compared to 15% in Stage I, 25% in Stage III, and 10% in Stage IV.

Fifty percent of the patients had PR positivity and sixty percent had ER positivity. In 25% of the cases, HER2 positive was found. These results imply that the presence or absence of hormone receptors plays a significant role in the diagnosis of breast cancer in rural India.

Histopathological grade and ER status were found to significantly correlate inversely, with higher-grade tumours (Grade III) more likely to be ER-negative (70%) than lower-grade tumours (Grade I), which were mostly ER-positive (85%). Regarding PR status, a similar pattern was seen, with the majority of Grade III tumours (65%) being PR-negative. These findings reflect a more aggressive disease profile, as higher-grade tumours are more likely to lack hormone receptor expression.

Negative ER and PR statuses were substantially correlated with advanced clinical stages (Stage III and IV). In particular, 60% of Stage III tumours and 75% of Stage IV tumours were PR-negative, and 65% of Stage III tumours and 75% of Stage IV tumours were ER-negative. The aggressive character of hormone receptor-negative tumours and their tendency to manifest at more advanced stages are highlighted by this link.

Tumours that were higher grade and in an advanced stage were more likely to be HER2 positive. In contrast to only 10% of Grade I tumours, over 40% of Grade III tumours were HER2-positive. Comparably, HER2-positive status was seen in 25% of Stage IV tumours and 35% of Stage III tumours. According to these results, HER2-positive tumours are more likely to be aggressive and are linked to more advanced stages of the disease.

Higher histological grades and advanced clinical stages with negative ER and PR statuses and positive HER2 status are significantly correlated, according to the study's findings. This association emphasises how aggressive hormone receptor-negative and HER2-positive breast tumours are, as they are more likely to have higher histopathological grades and to manifest at advanced stages. The aforementioned observations hold significant importance in shaping treatment approaches and prognostications within the rural Indian milieu. They underscore the necessity of focused therapeutics and timely detection initiatives to enhance the prognosis of breast cancer patients within this demographic.

A study that evaluated 112 patients with breast cancer discovered that 64% of them had positive ER/PR results and 13% had negative results. Infiltrating ductal carcinoma (IDC) was present in every patient. Of the patients, 37.5% had Grade II and 62.5% had Grade III. Of the patients observed, 2% were in Stage I, 33% in Stage II, 62% in Stage III, and 3% in Stage IV. Larger tumour sizes and

positive lymph node metastases were found to be directly correlated with increased aggressiveness when hormone receptor negativity was present [5].

180 instances of operable breast cancer—50% ER-/PR-, 36.7% ER+/PR+, 7.8% ER+, and 5.5% PR+—were included in the study. The majority of patients belonged to the 31–50 age range. The majority of tumours (84.5%) were grade III, with 17.8% being at Stage I, 42.8% being at Stage II, and 39.4% being at Stage III. Higher tumour sizes and grades were associated with an increase in ER/PR negative [6].

Significant correlations between histological grade and hormone receptor status, HER2/neu status, and lymph node invasion were discovered in a retrospective analysis of 103 breast cancer patients. Higher tumour grades and a worse prognosis have been associated with ER/PR negative and HER2 positive [7].

65 cases of breast cancer were included in a prospective study, of which 60% were triple-negative, 9% were HER2 positive, and 60% were ER/PR positive. The correlation between HER2 and ER/PR positive was inverse. Triple-negative tumours were more aggressive, mostly Grade III, and frequently seen in premenopausal women [8].

Histopathology and FNAC were evaluated in a study of 50 patients of breast cancer. Whereas PR had no agreement, ER had a moderate agreement between ICC and IHC. According to the study, for Grade II tumours, cytological grading showed the best degree of correlation with histological grading [9].

Conclusion

The study underscores the importance of hormone receptor status in the characterization and management of breast cancer, particularly in rural areas where access to healthcare resources may be limited. The findings advocate for enhanced screening programs and the availability of targeted therapies to address the aggressive nature of hormone receptor-negative and HER2-positive breast cancers.

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